

SETTING OF THE GELS OF SODIUM OLEATE AND STEARATE IN
SOME ORGANIC SOLVENTS. PART II. COOLING CURVES
OF SOAP-SOLVENT SYSTEMS

BY K. B. DESHPANDE AND K. P. BUCH

The study of the cooling curves of the solutions of sodium oleate and sodium stearate in nujol has shown that heat is evolved during gelation. The heat of gelation has been calculated for gels of different concentrations under various rates of cooling. It has been observed that the values of the ratio of the heat of gelation per gram molecule of soap to the temperature of setting in absolute units are very nearly constant, independent of the rate of cooling and the concentration of the soap.

The cooling curves for solutions of some soaps in water-alcohol mixtures and nujol (Fisher, *Kolloid Z.*, 1929, 48, 359; Lederer, *ibid.*, 1931, 57, 116; Lawrence, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1938, 34, 660) and ninene (Prasad *et al.*, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, 21A, 1; *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1946, 14, Part III, 23) have been studied systematically. It has been observed that in all cases heat is evolved at the point of setting of gels, and it is of the same order of magnitude as the heat evolved during solvation of soaps to alco-sols and hydro-sols [Prasad *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, Lederer, *loc. cit.*, Kandelaki, *Khim. Ref. Zhur*, 1941, 4 (6), 18; *Izvestiya Gruzinskogo Ind. Inst. Kerova*, 13, 109).

Prasad *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) also calculated from the cooling curves the specific heats of the gel-forming solutions just before and after gelation, and found that for the same concentration of soap, the specific heat of the sol state was greater than that of the corresponding gel, and that with the increase in the soap content of the systems, the specific heats in two states also increased.

However, all these observations do not include sufficient exhaustive data regarding the behaviour of any one of the systems under different conditions so as to point out definitely whether or not the process of gelation is comparable to the change of state. In order to study in detail the thermal change accompanying the process of gelation, the cooling curves of solutions of sodium oleate and stearate in nujol have been studied, and the observed results interpreted on theoretical basis.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials and the mode of preparation of gels used in this investigation are the same as those described in Part I of the series (this *issuc*, p. 321).

The cooling curves of the several systems of sodium oleate and sodium stearate in nujol were determined as follows: A thermometer was introduced in the centre of the test tube (2.6 cm. diam.) containing the gel-forming mixture, after the condensing column was removed and the tube was placed in a thermostat maintained at a constant temperature. A stop-watch was started immediately and the temperature of the gel-forming solution was noted at definite intervals of time (15

seconds). In order to obtain strictly comparable results with the solvent it was also heated in the same test tube to the same temperature as the solution and was allowed to cool in the thermostat maintained at the same temperature. Some of the results obtained are graphically represented in Figs. 1 and 2

FIG. 1

Sodium oleate in nujol. ($T=50^{\circ}$).

DISCUSSION

It can be seen that (i) up to a certain stage the cooling curves for solutions coincide more or less with those of the solvents and after this stage the solvents cool faster

than the solutions under identical conditions of cooling, and (ii) the higher the concentration of the soap, the slower is the rate of cooling of the solutions.

FIG. 2

Sodium stearate in nujol ($T=50^\circ$).

The curves for solutions show that they change their directions at two points in each curve, thus furnishing a kink in the curves. This indicates that heat is evolved during this stage. The time of setting determined by Flemming's method occurs during the range of the kink. This establishes that heat is evolved during the sol-gel transformation.

The evolution of heat can be explained on the basis of the theory of gel-formation. The soap particles in soap solutions are more or less in a molecular state and possess a definite amount of kinetic energy. On cooling, the solution undergoes saturation and supersaturation, which lead to the formation of colloid particles and their final agglomeration to the gel state. In this process a restriction would be imposed on the degree of freedom of motion of individual particles, which would lead to the reduction of kinetic energy; this is given out as heat of gelation.

The actual amount of the heat of gelation (H) has been calculated in each case from the relation,

$$H = \frac{S_1\theta_1 + S_2\theta_2}{2} \times t,$$

where S_1 and S_2 are the specific heats in the sol and the gel states, θ_1 and θ_2 are their respective rates of cooling and t , the time in seconds over which heat is evolved. The results obtained are recorded in Tables I and II. The results confirm that (i) for any one concentration of the soap, the specific heat in the sol state is greater than that in the gel state and (ii) the specific heats in the sol and the gel states of the same system increase with the increase in concentration of the soaps. Further, it will be observed that the heat of gelation increases as the soap content is increased. Also the heat of gelation of a system of a particular concentration is almost independent of the rate of cooling, that is, of the temperature of surroundings.

TABLE I
Sodium oleate in nujol.

C.	T.	S_1 .	S_2 .	H.	$T_R + 273$.	MH.	$\frac{MH}{T_R + 273}$
0.2	40°	1.5	1.3	29.14	412	44350	105.8
0.3	40°	1.8	1.5	42.72	423	43350	102.5
0.5	40°	2.1	1.6	67.96	428	41390	96.7
0.2	50°	1.6	1.3	28.62	412	43580	103.3
0.3	50°	2.0	1.6	40.10	423	40660	96.1
0.5	50°	2.2	1.7	70.30	428	42800	100.0
0.2	60°	1.7	1.4	28.30	412	42024	102.0
0.3	60°	2.0	1.7	40.00	423	40500	98.8
0.5	60°	2.3	1.7	67.63	428	41180	96.2

An interesting point is observed when the values of the ratio of the heat of gelation per gram molecule of soap to the temperature of setting in absolute units, recorded in the last column of Tables I and II, are examined. It will be seen that for the same system these are very nearly constant. Also there appears to be a vague similarity between these results and Trouton's rule, a generalisation according to which the ratio of the molar latent heat of vapourisation to the boiling point is constant for most substances.

TABLE II
Sodium stearate in nujol.

C.	T.	S ₁ .	S ₂ .	H.	T _R + 273.	MH.	$\frac{MH}{T_R + 273}$
0.2	40°	1.8	1.3	27.24	425.0	41680	98.1
0.8	40°	2.0	1.6	43.30	432.0	43860	100.5
0.4	40°	2.1	1.6	59.98	436.5	46350	106.2
0.2	50°	2.1	1.4	28.28	425.0	43140	101.5
0.3	50°	2.1	1.7	43.66	432.0	45570	105.5
0.4	50°	2.2	1.7	58.79	436.5	44970	103.0
0.2	60°	2.2	1.9	28.67	425.0	46920	100.4
0.3	60°	2.3	1.8	40.64	432.0	42420	98.2
0.4	60°	2.3	2.0	56.19	436.4	43840	100.4

One more striking observation that can be made on close examination of the curves is that in all the cases, the point of setting of the system of a gel, determined for a particular concentration by an independent method, lies in the middle or the end portion of the kink. This can be explained as follows: The thermometer records the temperature at the centre of the system which is higher than the temperature of the outermost layers in contact with the surrounding. This gives rise to a temperature gradient within the system, varying from the temperature recorded at the centre to the temperature of the surrounding. The gelation takes place in layers, and the heat of gelation evolved by the outermost layers retards the rate of cooling of the inner layers. Hence, the changes in direction of the curves at this stage are gradual. In the light of these observations, the setting point should lie at the end of the kink. However, this has not been realised because the setting observed by the inversion of the tube may be due to the setting of most of the outer layers and not necessarily of the entire systems.

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE, BOMBAY.

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